

Windows on the Universe: Establishing the Infrastructure for a Collaborative Multi-messenger Ecosystem

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Over the course of three days, 16–18 October, NSF’s NOIRLab, in partnership with NSF and NASA, held a workshop titled “[Windows on the Universe: Establishing the Infrastructure for a Collaborative Multi-messenger Ecosystem.](#)” Multi-messenger astronomy (MMA) uses some combination of electromagnetic radiation, gravitational waves, neutrinos, and cosmic rays to understand astrophysical phenomena more comprehensively than just one messenger would allow. The processes MMA is particularly suited for include massive star explosions, mergers of neutron stars and black holes, and tidal disruption events.

The workshop brought together more than 200 attendees, both in-person and virtually, from all around the world. The agenda included both invited and contributed talks, as well as panels and discussions to allow as much community input and engagement as possible. Researchers from a variety of multi-messenger observatories including ICECube, HAWC, LIGO, Swift, Hubble, JWST, NOIRLab, Keck, and MMT

(just to name a few) were present, as well as representatives from NSF and NASA, who were particularly interested in the outcomes of the workshop.

Over the course of the three days, the past, present, and future of multi-messenger astronomy were discussed, in particular how the infrastructure (software, hardware, and people) has worked and how it will need to be improved in the future to optimize the science return. NOIRLab staff who attended and presented at the meeting also took special note of how to help optimize NOIRLab facilities to be at the forefront of MMA. The focus of the workshop was on communication, cooperation, and collaboration. These three themes will also be at the forefront of the white paper that is being written to summarize the state of the field and to make recommendations to funding agencies for future ways forward.

This document will be relied on heavily by NSF in producing a spring solicitation for their [Windows on the Universe: The Era of Multi-Messenger Astrophysics \(WoU-MMA\)](#) funding opportunities.

Special thanks are due to the organizing committees for making this workshop successful!